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The Vaishnavite interpretation of the Indus Valley Pashupathi Seal

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Abstract.

Standard interpretations of the seals and images from the Indus Valley Civilization have struggled to understand the meanings and significance of the motifs. The best researchers across the world have struggled to find the meaning of the symbols of the Indus Valley Civilization. I argue that the lack of success is driven by a lack of understanding of Indian religious stories and an ignorance of how interconnected Indian spirituality and daily tradition is. I make the case for a story-based interpretation of Indus Valley seals and symbols. This has never been attempted so far. I use this technique on the Pashupati seal and the Buffalo Sacrifice Tablet to explain how an indecipherable seal becomes laden with meaning when interpreted the right way. I also propose that Vaishnavite and Shaivite worship is thousands of years older than commonly believed. The Pashupati seal is possibly full of Vaishnavite and Shaivite symbols which all modern scholars of Indian anthropology and religion may have completely missed. Using this new story-based model of interpreting India Valley seals could be the way to unlocking their true significance. It remains to be seen if this model can be used to unlock other seals. However, the direction has a lot of promise

Keywords: Pashupati Seal, Indus Valley, Shiva, Vaishnavite, Mohenjo-daro. Harappa

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1. Introduction

The Pashupati seal is one of the most celebrated steatite seals from Mohenjo-daro, Indus Valley Civilization, from around 2350 BCE. It is one of the most puzzling figures of the Indus Valley. Nobody has any idea what the image stands for. Most researchers seem to look at the image in abstract and hence make no progress.

Figure 1: Pashupati Seal

Source: Pashupati seal. (2024, June 29). In Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pashupati_seal

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2. Methods

The image is compared with respect to the religious motifs of Hindu religion. These are the points that emerge.

The person at the centre:

1. This is a person in an unmistakable Yoga pose. He is a Yogi engrossed in deep meditation. The image is that of the Adi Yogi. Adi Yogi is another name for Lord Shiva
2. This person has three faces, symbolizing Sattva, Rajas, and Tamas. The relief engraving hides other faces, but there could be more. He is the Trimukhi (the three faced) or Panchamukhi (five faced) which are other names for Lord Shiva.
3. The head has a three-pronged Trishul, signifying the three aspects of creation (Sattva), preservation (Rajas) and destruction (Tamas). Who possesses the Trishul? It is the favourite weapon of Lord Shiva.

The images around the central figure:

1. Many animals (Pasu) are nearby. Hence, this is the lord of animals, Pasupathi which is another name for Shiva.
2. There is even a long-horned cow bull. That is Shiva's vahana, Nandi,
3. There is an elephant nearby. Is that the lord of elephants, Gajanan? The trunk touches the person below, signifying their closeness. Is it a mother-son relationship?
4. A tiger nearby seems to spring on the Yogi. However, there seems to be a human-like figure with legs spread out as if the person was seated atop the tiger. This image is close to both the tiger and the elephant. Could the tiger be the mount and the elephant be related to this figure? It appears that this human is Shakti or Durga who has the tiger as her Vahana. She is the spouse of Shiva. Also, note that being seated on tiger skin is the make of a great yogi who has transcended his animal nature, though that is not depicted here.
5. The seat-stand looks strange. It is shaped like a damru, a sound-emitting instrument. Are the claws at the end of the damru meant to show movement?
6. There are a couple of big-horned rams at the bottom of the seal. Rams are the Vahana (vehicle) of fire Agni. So, the person is either a form of Agni (representing fire and destruction) or the lord of Agni.

The images at the top:

1. There is a one-horned (Ekashringa) rhinoceros or boar nearby. That is the Varaha or Ekkashringa form of Vishnu. Rhinos figurines were common in early Harappa. So rhinos being in the region of IVC should be of no surprise to anyone.
2. One can spot a fish hanging upside down. It cannot be anything other than a fish. The fish is a reference to the Matsya avatar of Vishnu.

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3. In one of the hieroglyphics, there is a familiar Vaishnavite Tilak that symbolizes Vishnu. The images of Vishnu and Shiva are both at the centre of the image meant to show that both are supreme and both equivalent.
4. A person above the rhinoceros has the rhino as the mount. This is a reference to the Krishna avatar of Vishnu.
5. There is an optical illusion in the picture where the person stands at the top corner. The hands, legs and symbols intersect at weird angles. Sometimes, the picture looks like a person with one leg behind and another leg outstretched. He seems ready to step on something, corresponding to the Vamana Avatar.

Figure 2: Rama and Parasurama avatar

6. The same image looks like someone holding a bow and axe contraption (stretched arrow on the left side by side with an axe on the right) in the hand, referring to the Parasurama Avatar of Vishnu. The axe is clearly visible on the hand if one ignores some protruding parts.
7. It could also be seen as a person wielding a stretched bow and arrow as in the case of the Rama Avatar of Vishnu. The axe is in front of the bow.
8. All four avatars. (Krishna, Vamana, Parasurama and Rama) are the human forms of Vishnu and have been consolidated into one image of the human.
9. There is a U-shaped symbol with a mark at the centre, right above the central image. seems to be a two-headed snake with its mouth open. That multi headed snake is Vasuki with the poison Halahala foaming from its mouth, which emerged during the great churning of the ocean. Halahala is linked to the story of Neelkanta, the name for Shiva when he drank the Halahala. That story represents the Kurma Avatar of Vishnu. The Kurma (turtle) is shown at the centre as a circular dot which is even above the snakes. The Kurma avatar is the base on which the Vasuki and Mount Mandara stood.
10. One of the symbols to the left of the centre seems most unclear. It is as if a headless person has something or somebody on their lap and, going by another symbol on the left, is about to axe them to death. There is a human body almost seated but not completely with the legs on the ground and something on the lap. The are smudges near the head and

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body possibly indicating that the image may have been chipped or broken. That is the Narasimha Avatar of Vishnu. The head may have chipped off and would have represented the face of a lion.

Figure 3: Vamana and Narasimha avatar

11. It is a remarkable coincidence that all the avatars of Vishnu have been represented in the images and each avatar is located next to each other. All of them except the Varaha avatar are located right next to each other.

3. Results

I have listed twenty inferences that can be made from the Pashupati seal. I have explained every single symbol on the seal with a clear logic and theme. This gives a completely novel hypothesis to start investigating. As far as I know, nobody in the world has ever interpreted the seal from a Vaishnavite and avatar-based perspective. Most people assume that Krishna emerged around two thousand years later and do not want to challenge their own biases and preconceptions. Krishna and Vaishnavism may have been far older than historians give credit for. If any of the fourteen points or were true, most of the Western interpretations of India and Hindu history would have to be discarded completely.

If true, this could mean that Indian stories from Puranas are many thousands of years older than thought. When the first empire emerged under Sargon the Great in Akkad in 2350 BCE, Indians already had a sophisticated empire that existed prior. These symbols, stories, and myths could mean that civilization emerged in India and China first and spread westward later.

So, how do these Western professors interpret this seal? Here are the words of Richard Meadow, an Indus Valley expert from Harvard University, who says he cannot find any meaning in the image and finds it incomprehensible.

"It is a rare but widely distributed motif on both intaglio seals (Mohenjo-daro) and moulded tablets (Harappa). Facts about each object include its archaeological context (if that context is known), what other depictions occur on the same artefact (associated motifs and

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"script"), what the artifact is made of, and what its shape is. In spite of much speculation in the literature, we have no actual idea of the meaning or significance of this image, because there is no way to verify any interpretation, especially in the absence of a widely accepted decipherment of the "script". Furthermore, an unbroken (without significant temporal gaps) line of use of the motif from the Indus period into the historical period has not been demonstrated." (Meadow, n.d.)

Here is an Indian expert, Shereen Ratnagar, an Indus Valley expert from Jawaharlal Nehru University. She says:

"...shows that field symbols 46-49 seated horned personage and animals/serpent or personage by himself occurs ONLY at Mohenjo-daro. He is shown by himself on three seals, With the rhino, buffalo, etc. on just one seal, and with a "kneeling adorant" and a rising snake on two seals. I don't know if recent excavations at Harappa have found this motif on any of their seals...if not, this is extremely significant for the role of Mohenjo-daro, don't you think?" (Ratnagar, n.d)

Shereen, a trained historian, cannot find any meaning other than the rhinos, buffalo, snakes, etc, which even any layman can perceive. A typical Western armchair researcher who has no idea of Indian history would think that the image is of a human probably wearing a hat with a pet unicorn standing side by side. They probably keep wondering where the unicorns came from. Therefore, they spend a lifetime researching unicorns in India and wonder why ancient Indians were so deluded about unicorns that never existed. This is the state of academic research about Indian history. Unless Indians come and interpret their own heritage with a feeling of Bhakti and devotion, nobody else will help them in this quest.

Replicability:

For those who still cannot accept that the image is of Shiva, look at this other image of Pashupati from the Indus Valley. This image is described on the official Harappa.com website thus:

"Plano convex molded tablet showing an individual spearing a water buffalo with one foot pressing the head down and one arm holding the tip of a horn. A gharial is depicted above the sacrifice scene and a figure seated in yogic position, wearing a horned headdress, looks on. The horned headdress has a branch with three prongs or leaves emerging from the centre."(Parpola, 2015)

This is an absolutely incompetent description from another self confessed western scholar of Hindutva. Even a child in India can see that this is no sacrifice, there is an important story in progress here. It is so important that the greatest and most joyous celebrations in India are held in the name of Durga Puja.

If this was an ordinary women fighting a buffalo, there are too many unanswered questions:

1. Women on the battlefield is a strange concept and rarely exhibited in any images. This has to be a special woman.
2. She also wields a powerful, large weapon shaped like a goad. Goad is a weapon found in almost all representations of Shakti to this day.

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3. To have a Yogi sit behind is even more quizzical, him without intervening in the fight. His image is ethereal, as if floating in the air.
4. The woman is on the offensive suggesting that it is not a case of an animal attacking a human. There should be a deeper story and significance to it.

Figure 4: The Buffalo Sacrifice Tablet

Source: <https://www.harappa.com/blog/buffalo-sacrifice>

The image depicts the final act of Shakti Durga killing Mahishasura. This is one of the most famous stories of the Hindu lexicon. Shiva represents the Paramatman, the observer consciousness inside all of us. He does not directly interfere in the actions of people, but guides them from the inside. This image is to show that Shiva is consciousness. This is a unique idea that was rediscovered in the 18th century Europe as German idealism. They were only replicating esoteric ideas that existed from the days of the Indus Valley.

Durga's victory depicts our inner consciousness transcending the Tamasic asuric impulses that exist all around us. The gharial is the symbol of water and the vahana of the River Ganga. The symbol may have been meant to accentuate the origins of Mahishasura, who was born from a water buffalo.

What are Shiva and Shakti together? There are allusions to modern Advaita. Just as Shakti and Siva are inseparable, our inner consciousness (Jivatman) and the consciousness of the world (Paramatman) are equally inseparable. Advaita and non-duality may not be a recent construct created by Gaudapada and Adi Shankaracharya, as the west believes. These ideas could have been present right from the dawn of Hindu thought, starting from at least 2350 BCE if not earlier.

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4. Discussion

A bunch of questions emerge from the Pashupati seal.

1. Was there really a conflict between the Shaivites and Vaishnavites in the beginning of Hindu civilization? Were differences between Vaishnavites and Shaivites a recent emergence?
2. Is the location of Vishnu and Shiva both together and at the centre of the Pashupati seal meant to reveal their absolute unity? Did the Indus Valley practice a form of Tantric Shaivism or pure Advaita? Was Advaita common during the early days of the Indus Valley civilization and where did these ideas emerge??
3. It is difficult to accept that Yoga was practised more than 5000 years ago. However, this seal clearly demonstrates that Yoga was well observed in the ancient times. The origin of Yoga seems to predate the Yogasutras and other known books on Yoga. The source of Yoga has to be investigated in even more detail as simple linear accounts will not suffice.

5. Conclusion

Care should be taken to credit the Indus Valley figures and seals with more religious and Hindu significance than has been historically provided. I have shown that at least two seals of Indus Valley script can be completely decoded by employing Hindu imagery and stories to fill the gap. This effort must be replicated with other seals and images. With a more devotional and respectful attitude, the unsolvable Indus Valley code can be encrypted.

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